

FACTORS INFLUENCING THE SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT MODEL OF FITNESS CLUBS IN SHANXI PROVINCE, CHINA

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Abstract

From the situation of fitness clubs in China in recent years, the fitness club industry has developed rapidly, but there are also many problems and shortcomings. The same is true for the fitness club industry in Shanxi Province, which is closely related to the sustainable management model of fitness clubs. Therefore, in-depth research and exploration of its influencing factors are particularly important and crucial. So, I have conducted systematic research on this aspect. The purpose of this study is to: (1) To study the current situation and influencing factors the sustainable management of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China. (2) To analyze factors positive influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China. (3) To examine and evaluate the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China. This study adopted a mixed research method that combines quantitative and qualitative methods. Step 1: In the qualitative research section, expert was used to investigate the current situation and influencing factors of sustainable management models of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province. Total of 15 participants. The tool used in this study is a structured interview. Step 2: In the quantitative research section, the sample consists of 396 respondents and is obtained through sampling. Use the method used to determine that the sample size is 20 times the inventory variable to calculate the sample size. Collect data using questionnaire survey method and analyze using structural equation modeling. Step 3: Through a combination of quantitative and qualitative research, 13 experts conducted focus group discussions and scoring. Experts have conducted a high-level evaluation of the feasibility, suitability, usefulness, and accuracy of the factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, and their opinions remain consistent. The research results indicate that: 1) The current situation the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province reflects the actual situation of the influencing factors of the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province. The fitness club industry in Shanxi Province is constantly developing and progressing, and the number of fitness participants is gradually increasing. By comprehensively analyzing these factors, the sustainable management level of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province can be further improved. 2) Organizational structure, employee training, benefit, innovative marketing, and community cooperation have a significant positive impact on the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province. 3) Experts unanimously agree that the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China. Is Feasibility, Useful, Appropriate, Accuracy in A lot level-The most level.

Keywords: Fitness Club, Sustainable Management Model, Organizational Structure, Employee Training, Benefit, Innovative Marketing, Community Cooperation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of sustainable management models for fitness clubs in Shanxi Province cannot be separated from many influencing factors, including organizational structure, employee training, benefit, innovative marketing, and community cooperation. These factors are intertwined and jointly construct the development pattern of sustainable management models for fitness clubs in Shanxi Province. Understanding these factors is crucial for gaining a deeper understanding of the future development direction of sustainable management models for fitness clubs in Shanxi Province. At present, domestic and foreign researchers mainly focus on qualitative research on the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, while neglecting quantitative research on the factors that affect their development. Therefore, in this study, the relationship between organizational structure, employee training, benefit, innovative marketing and community cooperation and the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province was studied, and a model of the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province was established.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Policies of fitness club in China

To promote the extension of public sports resources to the grassroots and improve the balance and balance of public sports resource allocation, it is not only necessary to sink sports resources and accurately meet the sports needs of the masses, but also to guide the masses to participate extensively and stimulate endogenous motivation. The "Shanxi province national fitness implementation plan (2021-2025)" (hereinafter referred to as the "Plan") proposes to achieve equalization of public sports services and strengthen the development of grassroots mass sports. Whether there is a reasonable sustainable management model is an important prerequisite for the healthy development of a fitness club.

As macro policy guidance for the fitness industry, the Shanxi Province National Fitness Implementation Plan have established the main tone for the development of the fitness club industry, pointed out the development direction, and laid a solid foundation for the stable and sustainable development of the fitness club industry.

2.2 The concept of sustainable management of fitness clubs

Lin (2021) argued in "On the Brand Building of Commercial Fitness Clubs in China" that the characteristics of commercial fitness clubs can be summarized as: commercial fitness clubs provide health and fitness services. Commercial fitness clubs are based on certain hardware conditions. Commercial fitness clubs are operating entities that operate in accordance with market laws and are responsible for their own profits and losses.

In Chen (2022)'s "Research on the characteristics of commercial sports and fitness clubs in China" a broad definition of fitness clubs mainly refers to "institutions or places that provide good fitness services and improve fitness facilities for members." Narrowly defined, a fitness club refers to a group indoor sports and entertainment venue that targets the middle and high-end sub healthy population, Adopting a membership based management system, advocates fashionable fitness as the slogan, and provides comprehensive services as the purpose.

2.3. Theoretical of sustainable management model of fitness clubs

Sustainable management refers to the management methods of fitness clubs to achieve long-term economic, social and environmental benefits. It is a comprehensive management concept and method that emphasizes the balance between economic growth, social development and environmental protection. The theory holds that the long-term success of health clubs depends not only on short-term economic benefits, but also on social and environmental sustainability. Li (2022)

2.4 The main factors affecting the sustainable business model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province.

In order to further clarify the factors that affect the sustainable management of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, and to further elucidate the relevant influencing factors of sustainable management of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province. Based on China's ethnic knowledge, five main factors that affect the sustainable management of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province have been formed: Organizational structure, Employee training, Benefit, Innovative marketing, and Community cooperation.

2.5 Related research

On the basis of analyzing the problems existing in the development of fitness clubs, this paper evaluates their gains and losses from the aspects of operational strategies, service systems, and coach team management. In order to promote the harmonious development of consumer ecology, in-depth theoretical discussions have been conducted, and new suggestions have been put forward for the sustainable development of fitness clubs, thereby promoting research on the sustainable development of fitness clubs (Liu, 2022).

Through the analysis of macro data, we can gain a deeper understanding of the operation of fitness clubs, draw on the operational cases of excellent fitness clubs, conduct precise positioning analysis, and provide correct guidance for the development of fitness clubs, in order to achieve better sustainable development (Lei, 2021).

2.6 Conceptual framework

This study takes Organizational structure, Employee training, Benefit, Innovative marketing, and Community cooperation as independent variables, and the dependent variable on the influencing factors of sustainable management models in fitness clubs. Based on literature review and research objectives, a model of the influencing factors of sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province was constructed. The figure shows a schematic diagram of this model.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual model

This conceptual model provides the basic hypothetical relationship between the five factors of Organizational structure, Employee training, Benefit, Innovative marketing, and Community cooperation and the influencing factors of sustainable management models in fitness clubs. Assuming the following:

H1: Organizational structure factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province.

H2: Employee training factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province.

H3: Benefit factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province.

H4: Innovative marketing factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province.

H5: Community cooperation factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The first step is for researchers to search for literature, books, theories, and related research on relevant professional disciplines both domestically and internationally. Collect data through interviews and use purposeful random sampling to select the target sample group, in order to understand and summarize the current situation and influencing factors of sustainable management of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, China. The second step is to use the Chinese

online questionnaire platform for data collection. Then use SmartPLS4 to analyze the collected questionnaire data, establish a structural equation model, and validate five hypotheses. The third step is focus group discussion. Through group discussions and expert discussions on opinions and information, the collected interview data related to the factors affecting the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, China will be coded for qualitative research. Using the sustainability evaluation table of factors influencing the sustainable model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, analyze the information in the focus group discussion through content analysis and quantitative research. Evaluate the feasibility, applicability, effectiveness, and accuracy of the sustainable management model for fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, China.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

Research on the influencing factors the sustainable business models of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, China. This article adopts a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods.

4.1 Qualitative analysis

This section studies the current situation and influencing factors of sustainable management of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, China. The following is an interview summary:

This study investigates the current situation of factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province. It is found that China has adopted various methods to ensure the sustainable management of fitness clubs, aiming to enhance the overall strength and industry competitiveness of fitness clubs. Shanxi Province has taken a series of effective measures in the management and construction of fitness clubs, aiming to optimize the business environment, management and development mechanism of fitness clubs, thereby improving the overall level of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province and cultivating fitness clubs with outstanding abilities in the current fierce competition. To improve the sustainable management level of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, it is necessary to start from the foundation and work together from multiple aspects. The standards and indicators for sustainable management of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province cover multiple aspects, including membership, operational efficiency, brand market, service quality, facility environment, human resources, social responsibility, innovation ability, and development potential. After research, it has been summarized that there are five factors that affect the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province: Organizational structure, Employee training, Benefit, Innovative marketing, and Community cooperation.

4.2 Quantitative analysis

4.2.1 Descriptive statistical analysis

The demographic characteristics of the respondents were analyzed in this study. The organization analyzed the basic information of the respondents and described the overall distribution of the sample from seven aspects: gender, age, nature of work, duration of work, highest education level, duration of participation in fitness clubs, and reasons for joining fitness clubs.

4.2.2 Reliability and validity analysis

Table 4.1 First-order construct reliability test results table

First-order construct	Number of measurement items	Cronbach's alpha
OSMA	5	0.847
OSC	5	0.890
OSME	5	0.880
ETT	5	0.870
ETP	5	0.864
ETC	5	0.881
BEV	5	0.904
BEG	5	0.869
BET	5	0.863
IMP	5	0.883
IMD	5	0.868
IMM	5	0.887
CCR	5	0.871
CCA	5	0.862
CCM	5	0.863
ECS	5	0.885
ENS	5	0.871
SS	5	0.876
Total	90	0.874

This study used Cronbach's Alpha test to investigate the reliability of the structure and sample dimensions. After testing, the lowest value of the Cronbach alpha coefficient is 0.847, which is greater than 0.7 and meets the corresponding judgment criteria. This study used KMO and Bartlett sphericity tests to verify the validity of the scale. The experimental results indicate that the five scales have good effects.

4.2.3 Validity analysis

Table 4.2 Validation Factor AVE and CR Index Values

Factor dimension	AVE	CR	Factor dimension	AVE	CR
Manager	0.677	0.851	Product and service innovation	0.681	0.884
Coach	0.695	0.891	Digital marketing	0.655	0.870
Member	0.622	0.882	Member experience	0.689	0.887
Theoretical knowledge	0.658	0.871	Resource Sharing	0.661	0.872
Professional skill	0.647	0.865	Activity cooperation	0.644	0.862
Communication skills	0.677	0.881	Membership expansion	0.647	0.864
Value for money	0.723	0.904	Economic sustainability	0.686	0.886
Group benefits	0.656	0.869	Environmental sustainability	0.660	0.872
Time efficiency	0.646	0.865	Social sustainability	0.669	0.877

This confirmatory factor analysis was conducted for a total of 18 factors and 90 analysis items. From the table, it can be seen that the AVE values corresponding to all 18 factors are higher than 0.5, and the CR values are also greater than 0.7, which fully indicates that the data analyzed in this study has good convergence effectiveness.

4.2.4 Structural Equation Model

This study used SmartPLS4.0 to establish a path model and imported the collected 396 sample data into it. The path model estimation diagram is shown in Figure.

Figure 4.1: research path model diagram

Table 4.3 Correlation analysis between variables

	OS	ET	BE	IM	CC	IFE
OS	0.870					
ET	0.414	0.872				
BE	0.549	0.532	0.874			
IM	0.388	0.515	0.285	0.890		
CC	0.270	0.650	0.376	0.494	0.877	
IFE	0.511	0.670	0.567	0.546	0.596	0.888

From the data in the table, we can see that the Pearson correlation coefficient between most variables is greater than 0, and there is a significant positive correlation. It can be concluded that there is a significant correlation between the variables. Therefore, the correlation of the variables is in line with the expected assumptions.

Table 4.4 Variable Interpretation Rate

	R-square	R-square Adjusted	Result
Factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs	0.963	0.962	High
Manager	0.746	0.745	High
Coach	0.768	0.767	High
Member	0.759	0.759	High
Theoretical knowledge	0.766	0.765	High
Professional skill	0.745	0.744	High
Communication skills	0.770	0.769	High
Value for money	0.809	0.808	High
Group benefits	0.739	0.738	High
Time efficiency	0.744	0.743	High
Product and service innovation	0.791	0.790	High
Digital marketing	0.789	0.788	High
Member experience	0.795	0.794	High
Resource Sharing	0.755	0.754	High
Activity cooperation	0.746	0.745	High
Membership expansion	0.808	0.807	High
Economic sustainability	0.602	0.602	High
Environmental sustainability	0.803	0.802	High
Social sustainability	0.647	0.646	High

The calculation results show that the predictive explanatory rate of the five independent variables of organizational structure, employee training, benefit, innovative marketing and community cooperation in the model on the influencing factors of sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province is 0.963, higher than 0.330, belonging to the level above explanatory level.

Table 4.5 Variable prediction determination coefficient

	F-square	Result
Organizational structure	0.041	High
Employee training	0.074	High
Benefit	0.063	High
Innovative marketing	0.056	High
Community cooperation	0.062	High

The calculation results show that the predictive coefficients of the five variables: organizational structure, employee training, benefit, innovative marketing and community cooperation for the dependent variable are all higher than 0.02, indicating that the predictive performance of the model is good.

Table 4.6 Predicted correlation scores

	SSO	Residual Sum of Squares (SSE)	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)	Result
Factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs	1188	632.293	0.468	High
Organizational structure	1188	1188	0	low
Manager	1980	1053.507	0.468	High
Coach	1980	946.638	0.522	High
Member	1980	976.662	0.507	High
Employee training	1188	1188	0	low
Theoretical knowledge	1980	989.327	0.5	High
Professional skill	1980	1027.719	0.481	High
Communication skills	1980	968.288	0.511	High
Benefit	1188	1188	0	low
Value for money	1980	852.273	0.57	High
Group benefits	1980	1021.274	0.484	High
Time efficiency	1980	1024.43	0.483	High
Innovative marketing	1188	1188	0	low
Product and service innovation	1980	922.555	0.534	High
Digital marketing	1980	955.141	0.518	High
Member experience	1980	913.268	0.539	High
Community cooperation	1188	1188	0	low
Resource Sharing	1980	1004.678	0.493	High
Activity cooperation	1980	1033.911	0.478	High
Membership expansion	1980	955.369	0.517	High
Economic sustainability	1980	925.822	0.532	High
Environmental sustainability	1980	939.13	0.526	High
Social sustainability	1980	958.908	0.516	High

In the structural model, Q² represents the predicted correlation of variables, and the larger the value, the stronger the predicted correlation.

The calculation results show that the Q² statistical correlation between the variables and the factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China is 0.468, indicating that the selected organizational structure, employee training, benefit, innovative marketing, community cooperation have a high predictive effect on the dependent variable of the factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China.

4.2.5 Structural model path coefficients/relationships

Table 4.7 Hypothesis Testing

Assumption	Path relationship	path coefficient	T	P value	Decide
Assumption	Organizational structure -> factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China	0.223	3.611	0.000	Supported
Assumption	Employee training -> factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China	0.304	4.923	0.000	Supported
Assumption	Benefit -> factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China	0.261	4.583	0.000	Supported
Assumption	Innovative marketing -> factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China	0.253	4.410	0.000	Supported
Assumption	Community cooperation -> factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China	0.265	4.716	0.000	Supported

The direct effect test is shown in the table: organizational structure has a significant positive impact on the factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China ($\beta = 0.223$, $t=3.611 > 1.960$, $P=0.000 < 0.05$), assuming H1 is validated. employee training has a significant positive impact on the factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China ($\beta = 0.304$, $T=4.923 > 1.960$, $P=0.000 < 0.05$), assuming H2 is validated. Assuming H3 is validated, benefit significantly positively affects the factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China ($\beta = 0.261$, $T=4.583 > 1.960$, $P=0.000 < 0.05$). The innovative marketing has a significant positive impact on the factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China ($\beta = 0.253$, $T=4.410 > 1.960$, $P=0.000 < 0.05$), H4 was validated. Community cooperation has a significant positive impact on the factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China ($\beta = 0.265$, $T=4.716 > 1.960$, $P=0.000 < 0.05$), assuming H5 is validated.

4.3 Qualitative and quantitative analysis

This stage aims to examine and evaluate the influencing factors of the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province. The qualitative research section of this study used interview methods to select respondents for investigation, organized interview data, and analyzed the data. A quantitative study is conducted to evaluate the feasibility, practicality, suitability, and accuracy of the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province using the sustainability evaluation table of the influencing factors of the sustainable development model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province.

4.3.1 Research result

Research has found that the influencing factors of the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, as a core category of development direction, can connect and explain the correlation between various categories. Therefore, the researchers constructed a theoretical model of the influencing factors of the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, with organizational structure, employee training, efficiency, innovative marketing, and community cooperation as the core. Experts unanimously agree that the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi province, China. Is Feasibility, Useful, Appropriate, Accuracy.in A lot level-The most level. Be seen that the above content is an important influencing factor for the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, China.

5. CONCLUSION, DISCUSSION AND SUGGESTION

5.1 Conclusion

In the development process of the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, the five factors of Organizational structure, Employee training, Benefit, Innovative marketing, and Community cooperation have a significant positive impact on the development of the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province. The results of this study confirm that the factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province are closely related to their five components. Therefore, this study helps to use structural equation modeling to measure the factors influencing the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province in various ways. Among the factors that affect the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, the better ones can promote the development of the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, and have a greater impact on the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, thereby promoting the development of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, China.

5.2 Discussion

This study constructed structural equation model for the influencing factors of sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, and found that organizational structure, employee training, benefit, innovative marketing, and community cooperation have a significant positive impact on it. The study also found that fitness clubs in Shanxi Province have problems such as unreasonable organizational structure, inadequate employee training, unreasonable benefit allocation, insufficient innovative marketing, and insufficient community cooperation. Based on this, the study proposes corresponding suggestions, including optimizing organizational structure, strengthening employee training, allocating benefits reasonably, innovating marketing strategies, and deepening community cooperation.

5.3 Suggestion

Strengthen organizational structure development, optimize employee training system, improve benefit level, strengthen innovative marketing capabilities, improve the effectiveness of cooperation with the community. The purpose of this study is to explore in depth the

influencing factors of the sustainable management model of fitness clubs in Shanxi Province, China. Subsequent researchers will also attempt to conduct relevant research on the influencing factors of sustainable management models of fitness clubs in other countries and regions, and will compare and analyze the results of this study to expand the external validity of the research.

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